

Dependence of Zeta-potential on Equicoagulating Concentrations of Added Counter Ions for some Hydrophobic Sol Systems

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An equation of the form, $\zeta_a = A + B \log \sum c_i$, has been proposed to relate the dependence of measured ζ -potentials (ζ_a) on the equicoagulating concentrations of the added counter ions (c_i), taking surface-conductance effect into consideration. It has been found that there is a limiting concentration of the added counter ions after which the surface-conductance effect vanishes.

The measurement of ζ -potential of colloidal particles on the basis of the Helmholtz-Smoluchowski equation has been questioned as this does not yield a constant value in case of a particular sol in presence of different electrolytes of varying concentrations. The deviations were, in different times, attributed to different factors, such as (i) relaxation effect¹, (ii) surface-conductance effect², and (iii) electroviscous effect³.

Various mathematical relations have been proposed for the above effects. The limitation that has been ascribed to the relaxation effect⁴ is that this is considerable only when kr (k = reciprocal thickness of the double layer and r = radius of a single particle) lies between 0.1 and 100. Therefore this effect will be negligible when the concentration of the electrolyte in the system is comparatively large so that kr is greater than 100. Hunter and Alexander⁵ pointed out that the electroviscous effect was not very prominent when water was the dispersion medium. Ghosh⁶⁻⁷ considered the surface-conductance effect and proposed equations for correcting both electro-osmotic and electrophoretic ζ -potentials at equicoagulating concentrations of electrolytes. His equations had been amply verified in cases of different hydrosols, some of which have been quoted (*vide infra*).

Though a good deal of investigations had been carried out regarding the determination of the ζ -potential from electrokinetic measurements, yet the dependence of ζ -potential on the concentrations of the added counter ions in case of sol is hardly, if not at all, known. In the present communication the authors have tried to relate the measured ζ -potential with the concentrations of electrolytes containing different valent counter ions required at equicoagulating concentrations, taking into consideration sufficient published data on sols as well as their own data on silver bromide and manganese ferrocyanide sols under conditions in which surface-conductance effect is only present.

1. Overbeek, "Colloid Science", Vol I, edited by H. R. Kruyt, Elsevier, 1960, p. 210.
2. Bikermann, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1940, **35**, 155; Rutgers, *ibid.*, 1940, **35**, 69;
3. Booth, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1950, **A203**, 533; Lyklema and Overbeek, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1961, **16**, 501.
4. Overbeek, "Colloid Science", Vol. I, 1960, p. 211.
5. *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1963, **18**, 820.
6. Ghosh, *Naturwiss.*, 1955, **5**, 121; this *Journal*, 1955, **32**, 402.
7. Ghosh *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1955, **32**, 29.

EXPERIMENTAL

Silver Bromide Sol.—The negatively charged sol was prepared by following a slight modification of Basinski's method⁸. A 0.55% AgNO_3 solution was slowly added with constant stirring from a burette to a 0.5% KBr solution until the precipitate peptised with difficulty. This was then purified by electro-dialysis. Then to one portion a small volume of 0.5*N*- KBr solution (sol 2) was added and the other portion was kept as it was (sol 1). Both the portions were allowed to age for 15 days. The whole operation was performed in a dark room and containers were wrapped with black paper. The resulting sols were found to possess specific conductances of 1.67×10^{-4} (sol 1) and 8.034×10^{-4} (sol 2) $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ at 25°.

Manganese Ferrocyanide Sol.—The sol was prepared by precipitating manganese ferrocyanide by mixing manganous chloride with potassium ferrocyanide, both having concentration $M/10$, washing the precipitate with distilled water, peptising with a little ferrocyanide, and dialysing for a month. After aging for 7 days, the sol, thus obtained, was found to possess a negative charge and specific conductance of 2.25×10^{-4} $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ at 25°.

Determination of Equicoagulating Concentrations of Counter Ions and Measurement of ζ -Potential.—The sol (2 ml) was mixed with an electrolyte (2 ml) of known concentration. The mixture was allowed to stand for a specified time (30 min. in the case of silver bromide sols and 10 min. and 20 hr. in the case of manganese ferrocyanide sol) and then centrifuged for 2 min. The supernatant solution was tested for transparency. The concentration of the counter ion, which formed just transparent supernatant solution, was taken as the equicoagulating concentration of that counter ion.

The ζ -potentials of silver bromide sols were measured by microcataphoretic method as described by Chakravarti and Ghosh⁹. The results are plotted in Fig. 3 and 4.

The ζ -potentials of manganese ferrocyanide sol were measured both by electro-osmosis and electrophoresis. The electro-osmotic and electrophoretic methods followed were the same as described by Mukherjee *et al.*¹⁰ and Ghosh *et al.*¹¹ respectively. The results are plotted in Fig. 1 and 2.

DISCUSSION

At equicoagulating concentrations of electrolytes used for a definite rate of coagulation, the specific surface conductance (κ) of the coagulated and assumed insulated sol particles should remain constant. But the measured ζ -potential has been found to decrease with the decreasing value of $c_i z_i$, where c_i and z_i are the concentration in moles per liter and valence of the i -th type of counter ion, respectively, meaning thereby an increase of total surface-conductance effect with decreasing $c_i z_i$, or simply c_i , where c_i should represent concentration in equivalents per litre. This is because of the flow of greater amount of electricity through the surface of the coagulated sol particles than

8. *Roczniki Chem.*, 1947, **21**, 29.

9. *This Journal*, 1963, **40**, 425.

10. *Ibid.*, 1927, **4**, 493.

11. Ghosh *et al.*, *Kolloid Z.*, 1958, **158**, 45.

that through the bulk of the electrolyte solution. Evidently, the current causing the electrokinetic movement of the fluid on the slipping plane will be comparatively less prominent, producing thereby a greater decrease in the value of the measured ζ -potential with decreasing c_1 .

FIG. 1

Curve 1.1—Arsenious trisulphide sol—rapid rate—electro-osmosis.
 Curve 1.2—Lanthanum trioxide sol—rapid rate—electro-osmosis.
 Curve 1.3—Lanthanum trioxide sol—slow rate—electrophoresis.

FIG. 2

Curve 2.1—Titanium dioxide sol—rapid rate—electro-osmosis.
 Curve 2.2—Hydrogen mica sol—slow rate—electro-osmosis.
 Curve 2.3—Hydrogen mica sol—slow rate—electrophoresis.
 Curve 2.4—Uranyl ferrocyanide sol—rapid rate—electro-osmosis.
 Curve 2.5—Uranyl ferrocyanide sol—slow rate—electro-osmosis.
 Curve 2.6—Uranyl ferrocyanide sol—slow rate—electrophoresis.

To investigate this effect one is to carry out experiments under conditions in which mainly the actual value, *i.e.*, the theoretical value, of the ζ -potential should remain the same, or in other words, the charge density on the surface of the colloidal particles is the same. One can visualise this at equicoagulating concentrations of counter ions where the effectivity of the surface conductance will vary only with the concentration of the counter ions.

The surface conductance should arise out of the orientation of the excess charges at the surface of the colloidal particles. At the equicoagulating concentrations of different electrolytes, the surface of the colloidal particles should experience the same type of orientation of these counter ions which will cause the effective neutralisation of the surface charge to the same extent. This excess will be negligible when the bulk concentrations of the counter ions, *i.e.*, c_i is high. Hence the orientation of the counter ions at the surface will solely determine the variations in the effective surface conductance and hence the measured ζ -potential.

Then, for a particular rate of coagulation, the measured ζ -potential (ζ_a) may be given by the relation:

$$\zeta_a = \zeta - \zeta_d \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where ζ and ζ_d are the potentials absolute and the extent decreased due to surface-conductance effect, respectively.

It may be observed from the figures that in each case the ζ -potential increases with increasing concentrations of the counter ions where the concentrations are expressed in equivalents per litre. Since ζ cannot increase, this increase of ζ_a should be due to the decrease in the value of ζ_d . This leads to the assumption that the rate of decrease of ζ_d may depend inversely on the concentration of the added counter ion. Mathematically this is represented as:

$$\frac{-d\zeta_d}{dc_i} \propto \frac{1}{c_i} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

Integration of this equation gives

$$\zeta_d = -B' - B \log c_i \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where B' and B are constants.

Combining equation (3) with equation (1) one can obtain the following relation:

$$\zeta_a = \zeta + B' + B \log c_i \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

or

$$\zeta_a = A + B \log c_i \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

where $A = \zeta + B' = \text{constant}$.

To be more general, equation (5) should be written as

$$\zeta_a = A + B \log \Sigma c_i \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

where Σc_i takes into consideration the concentration terms of all the counter ions.

According to equation (6) the plot of ζ_a against $\log \Sigma c_i$ should yield a straight line.

The data published by Ghosh on arsenious sulphide¹² sol, Ghosh and De on lanthanum oxide¹³ and uranyl ferrocyanide¹⁴ sols, Ghosh on hydrogen mica¹⁵ sol, and Ghosh and Rakshit on titanium dioxide¹⁶ sol have been used by the authors and are represented in Fig. 1. and 2. In Fig. 3 are represented the data on silver bromide and manganese ferrocyanide sols. The figures establish the above relation for the above mentioned sols at particular rates of coagulation from electro-osmotic and/or electrophoretic measurements.

FIG. 3

- | | | | |
|-------------------------|--|--------------------|--|
| Curve 3.1—Pts. | 1. KNO_3 . | Curve 3.2—Pts. | 1. $\text{KNO}_3 + \text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. |
| (Silver bromide | 2. $\text{KNO}_3 + \text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. | (Silver bromide | 2. $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. |
| sol 1; rapid rate; | 3. $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. | sol 2; rapid rate; | 3. $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + \text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$. |
| microcata- | 4. $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + \text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$. | microcata- | 4. $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$. |
| phoresis). | 5. $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$. | phoresis). | |
| Curve 3.3—Pts. | 1. KCl . | Curve 3.4—Pts. | 1. KCl . |
| (Manganese ferro- | 2. $\text{KCl} + \text{BaCl}_2$. | (Manganese ferro- | 2. $\text{KCl} + \text{BaCl}_2$. |
| cyanide; rapid | 3. $\text{KCl} + \text{AlCl}_3$. | cyanide; slow | 3. $\text{KCl} + \text{BaCl}_2$. |
| rate; osmosis) | 4. BaCl_2 . | rate; osmosis), | 4. $\text{BaCl}_2 + \text{AlCl}_3$. |
| | 5. $\text{KCl} + \text{AlCl}_3$. | | |
| | 6. AlCl_3 . | | |
| Curve 3.5—Pts. | 1. KCl . | | |
| (Manganese ferro- | 2. $\text{KCl} + \text{BaCl}_2$. | | |
| cyanide; slow | 3. $\text{KCl} + \text{BaCl}_2$. | | |
| rate; electrophoresis). | 4. $\text{BaCl}_2 + \text{AlCl}_3$. | | |
| | 5. BaCl_2 . | | |

Limitations of the Equation.—Since equation (6) has been derived on the basis of the application of surface-conductance effect, it should obviously hold good up to the concentration of the counter ion used at which the effect of surface conductance vanishes. As this limiting value is difficult to reach by experimental performance, one can, however, obtain the same by taking recourse to the equation of Ghosh *et al.*⁶⁻⁷, both for electro-os-

12. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1953, **49**, 1477.13. *This Journal*, 1958, **35**, 837.14. *Ibid.*, 1949, **36**, 171.15. *Proc. Natl. Inst. Sci. (India)*, 1960, **26**, 441.16. *Science & Culture*, 1952, **18**, 498.

mosis and electrophoresis, as the case may be. The extrapolation of the $\zeta_0 - \log \Sigma c_i$ curve up to the corrected ζ -potential (corrected for surface conductance from Ghosh's relation) will then yield the concentration value at which surface-conductance effect vanishes. This limiting concentration may vary from sol to sol, depending on the composition of the sol particles and the nature and concentration of the stabilising electrolyte.

FIG. 4

Curve 4.1—Pts.	1. KNO ₃ .	Curve 4.2—Pts.	1. KNO ₃ + Ba(NO ₃) ₂ .
(Silver bromide sol-1; rapid rate; microcataphoresis).	2. KNO ₃ + Ba(NO ₃) ₂ .	(Silver bromide sol 2; rapid rate; microcataphoresis).	2. Ba(NO ₃) ₂ .
	3. Ba(NO ₃) ₂ .		3. Ba(NO ₃) ₂ + Al(NO ₃) ₃ .
	4. Ba(NO ₃) ₂ + Al(NO ₃) ₃ .		4. Al(NO ₃) ₃ .
	5. Al(NO ₃) ₃ .		
Curve 4.3—Pts.	1. KCl.	Curve 4.4—Pts.	1. KCl.
(Manganese ferrocyanide; rapid rate; osmosis).	2. KCl + BaCl ₂ .	(Manganese ferrocyanide; slow rate; osmosis).	2. KCl + BaCl ₂ .
	3. KCl + AlCl ₃ .		3. KCl + BaCl ₂ .
	4. BaCl ₂ .		4. BaCl ₂ .
	5. KCl + AlCl ₃ .		5. BaCl ₂ + AlCl ₃ .
	6. AlCl ₃ .		
Curve 4.5—Pts.	1. KCl.		
(Manganese ferrocyanide; slow rate; electrophoresis).	2. KCl + BaCl ₂ .		
	3. KCl + BaCl ₂ .		
	4. BaCl ₂ .		
	5. BaCl ₂ + AlCl ₃ .		

The equations of Ghosh are:

$$1/\zeta_0 = 1/\zeta + m/S \quad \dots \quad (7) \text{ for electro-osmosis}$$

$$1/\zeta_0 = 1/\zeta + m'/S \quad \dots \quad (8) \text{ for electrophoresis}$$

where m and m' are constants, S is the bulk specific conductance and other terms bear the usual significance. In the case of silver bromide and manganese ferrocyanide sols, $1/\zeta_0$ values are plotted against $1/S$ values in Fig. 4 to obtain the corrected ζ -value from the intercepts on the $1/\zeta_0$ axis. These corrected values and those reported in the published papers in the case of other sols have been utilised to find out the limiting concentration values of the sols. These are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Sol.	Time of coagulation.	Corrected ζ (mv).		Limiting conc. (N).		Mean conc. (N).
		Electro-osmosis.	Electrophoresis.	Electro-osmosis.	Electrophoresis.	
Arsenious sulphide	25 - 30 sec.	46.0 mv	..	8.51×10^{-2}	..	8.51×10^{-2}
Lanthanum oxide	15 min.	32.2	..	1.00×10^{-1}	..	..
	20 hr.	..	35.1 mv	..	1.00×10^{-1}	1.00×10^{-1}
Uranyl ferrocyanide	10 min.	23.7	..	2.19×10^{-2}	..	1.57×10^{-2}
	20 hr.	25.1	25.5	1.26×10^{-2}	1.26×10^{-2}	..
Hydrogen mica	20 hr.	35.0	35.0	1.95×10^{-2}	1.70×10^{-3}	..
Titanium dioxide	30 min.	27.8	..	1.18×10^{-2}	..	1.18×10^{-2}
Silver bromide (sol 1)	30 min.	..	28.6	..	5.01×10^{-2}	5.01×10^{-2}
Do (sol 2)	30 min.	..	31.6	..	13.36	13.36
Manganese ferrocyanide	10 min.	20.0	..	2.33×10^{-2}	..	1.71×10^{-2}
	20 hr.	26.7	27.8	1.59×10^{-2}	1.20×10^{-2}	..

As the limiting concentration values for different rates and also for different methods of measurements for a particular sol are very near to each other, a mean value has been computed. This mean value indicates that when this concentration of the counter ions will be exceeded, the ζ -potential will show no further change due to surface conductance.

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